

Observations on the King's Chamber Dimensions

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Abstract

Observations on the dimensions of the Great Pyramid's King's Chamber, as they relate to $\sqrt{5}$, the golden ratio φ , and π .

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, Great Pyramid, History of Mathematics, History of Science, π .

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1 Introduction

The King's Chamber in the Great Pyramid is notable for its blandness and absence of anything "interesting" other than the empty coffer. It is the plain sister compared to the grandeur of, say that of Rameses IV in the Valley of the Kings.

Instead of focusing on what is not there, we should look at what is there. For example,

- The coffer dimensions, discussed in *Khufu's Coffin* [1].
- The coffer's location, discussed in *The Original Location of Khufu's Coffin* [2].
- The wall block patterns, discussed in *The Writing is on the Wall* [3].
- The floor block patterns, discussed in *The King's Chamber Floor, Decoded* [4].
- The air shafts: position and function (work in progress).
- The chamber dimensions: length, breadth, heights, areas, volume, etc., discussed in this article.

In his paper, *Ancient metrication of the King's Chamber inside the Great Pyramid* [5], Robin Spivey summarises what we know about the dimensions of the king's chamber, from a design point of view.

Spivey also makes the case that the designers were aware of the metre, and chose dimensions that highlight this knowledge.

In this paper, I present more observations, particularly the interplay between φ and $\sqrt{5}$, and metres and cubits.

"All is number."

Pythagoras

"The language of Giza is mathematics."

Robert Bauval

"You will believe."

The architects of Giza

2 Symbols and values

Giza is a construction site. Construction is a practical art, so we need to use practical values for certain irrationals.

Symbol	Name	Practical value	% Accuracy	Date
π	Archimedes' constant	3.1416	99.9998	3.1416 < 150 BCE
τ	Circle constant	6.2832 = 2π	99.9998	
e	Euler's number	2.72 or 2.7183	99.9368 or 99.9993	1683 CE
ϕ	Golden ratio	1.618 $\phi + 1 = \phi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979	500 BCE ?
ρ	Plastic ratio	1.3247 $\rho + 1 = \rho^3 = 2.3247$	99.9986	1924 CE
$\sqrt{2}$	Root 2	1.414 or 1.4142	99.9849 or 99.999	
$\sqrt{3}$	Root 3	1.732	99.9971	
$\sqrt{5}$	Root 5	2.236	99.9970	
€	Royal cubit aka cubit	0.5236m ($\pi/6$)		
P	Petrie inch	2.5399977 cm		

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

I use "cubit" for the Royal cubit (€). The irrationals are interchangeably pure numbers, or lengths, depending on the context.

We should remember that we are dealing with a different culture, which may have had a different approach to accuracy and precision, compared to our modern scientific mindset. My Giza analysis suggests they typically worked to 3 or 4 decimal places. This may indicate that they used abacuses or counting tables, or possibly slide rules or logarithms, to calculate. Alternatively, they may just have used four decimals as anything more did not make sense in construction. 0.0001 € is $5.236 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}$, which is about 50 microns, half the smallest distance that can be seen with the naked eye, and approaching the length of a human liver cell.

Microns	Metres	Cubits	Description
4	< 0.00000400	< 0.00000760	clay grain
17	0.00001700	0.000003247	Minimum width of strand of human hair
30	0.00003000	0.000057295	Length of a human skin cell
50	0.00005000	0.000095492	Typical length of a human liver cell
60	0.00006000	0.000114591	Length of a sperm cell
62 - 4	0.000062 - 0.000004	0.0001184 - 0.0000076	silt grain
100	0.00010000	0.000190985	Smallest distance visible to naked eye
125 - 62	0.000125 - 0.000062	0.0002387 - 0.0001184	very fine grained sand
181	0.00018100	0.000345683	Maximum width of strand of human hair
200	0.00020000	0.000381970	Typical length of Paramecium caudatum
250 - 125	0.00025 - 0.000125	0.0004775 - 0.0002387	fine grained sand
500 - 250	0.0005 - 0.00025	0.0009549 - 0.0004775	medium grained sand
500	0.00050000	0.0009549	Typical length of Amoeba proteus
1000 - 500	0.0010 - 0.00050	0.0019 - 0.0009549	course grained sand
2000 - 1000	0.0020 - 0.0010	0.0038 - 0.0019	very course grained sand

Table 2: Putting small distances in perspective

This paper includes various formulas, which simultaneously represent lengths in cubits or metres.

The concept that a distance is also a number or formula is fundamental to understanding Giza.

3 Lengths as formulas

"Number, number, all is number."

Pythagoras, paraphrasing Ecclesiastes

Assume that one day in the future we land on a distant planet. We find what is clearly a measuring device, similar to a short metre stick. Nearby are a collection of large rock cubes. The ruler and cubes indicate that an intelligent society lived on this planet.

The ruler is marked into 100 divisions in groups of 10, and even though we are not familiar with the digit markings, we recognise a base-10 system. The ruler is about half as long as a metre stick, so each of the 100 graduations is about half a centimetre, and each tenth of those about half a millimetre.

We measure the first cube with the ruler, and observe that each side is 3.142 units. We recognize that number immediately, and also that the society was familiar with π .

We measure the next cube, which has a side of 6.283 units. We recognise that as 2π . We continue measuring the cubes, and find sizes of 1.618, 1.414, 1.732, and 2.236. We recognise all these numbers, and marvel at their accuracy and workmanship.

The next cube we measure has a side of 4.399 units. We do not recognise this number, and decide that the stone mason just picked a random size, or perhaps intended 4.40. If the other cubes did not exist, we might be correct. However, if we asked the ship's computer about 4.399, it would immediately inform us that 4.399 is $10\sqrt{5} \div \pi\varphi$, rounded to 3 decimals.

We measure the next cube, which has a side of 4.109 units. The ship's computer advises that 4.109 is $10\sqrt{5} \div \pi\sqrt{3}$, rounded to 3 decimals. We start to see a pattern. We measure the next cube, which has a side of 1.87 units. The computer tells us that this is $\frac{\pi\varphi}{e}$.

The last cube has a side of 4.347 units. The computer thinks for a while, then announces that 1.87 times the plastic ratio cubed is 4.347, rounded to 3 decimals.

Exploring further, we find two very large pyramids. We measure their bases, and find that one is 440 units, and the other 411 units. We think back to the stone cubes, and realise that 100 times 4.399 is 440, rounded to whole units, and 100 times 4.109 is 411, rounded to whole units. We ask the computer what it can tell us about 411 and 440. The computer replies that you can make a nearly perfect right-angled triangle with sides 50π , 411, and 440, with π at 3.142 [6].

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi e &= 4.398 \\ 10/(1 + \sqrt{\varphi}) &= 4.401 \\ \pi\varphi^2/2 &= 4.112 \\ 10/((\sqrt{2}(e-1))) &= 4.115 \\ 10\sqrt{5}/\pi e &\approx 2.618\end{aligned}$$

It takes a society a long time to develop to the point that they are dealing with the mathematics of compound interest or the golden ratio. For example, they would need writing materials, which implies a written language, as well as a societal structure that provided an educational system, which requires a certain level of economic development and market system. Such structures do not develop overnight.

At Giza, lengths are not just lengths, but have meaning. This could be either as a "plain" number like $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$, used in the Legon triangle [7] (Fig. 1), $\sqrt{5}$ used for the double-square site plan [8] (Fig. 2), or more complex formulas like those for 440, 411, and indeed 1.87 and $1.87\rho^3$, which we shall see again shortly.

Figure 1: The Legon Triangle from P1 to P3

4 Salient points from Spivey's paper

Spivey points out, inter alia, that:

1. The diagonals of the long walls are $5\sqrt{21}$ G, effectively 12 metres (11.997 m). The chamber design is the most sensible and practical way to achieve an "integer" length in metres.
2. The chamber height, from floor to ceiling, is $\sqrt{125}$ G, which is effectively 11.18 G. We could also write this as $\sqrt{5^3}$, $(\sqrt{5})^3$, or $5\sqrt{5}$.
3. The diagonal of the short walls is effectively 15 G.

Figure 2: The Giza site plan

4. The distance from any corner to the one opposite, in 3-D space, is 25 \mathcal{C} , or $5^2 \mathcal{C}$.
5. There is a classic 3-4-5 triangle design embedded in the short diagonal (15), length (20), and chamber diagonal (25).

Figure 3: Classic 3-4-5 Pythagoras triangle in the King's Chamber

5 The Golden Ratio: $\sqrt{5}$ and φ

The chamber is generally accepted to have a design size of 20 \mathcal{C} by 10 \mathcal{C} . Indeed, Petrie used those values to calculate the length of the cubit.

In his standard reference, *The Pyramids and Temples of Gizeh* [9] (§155), Petrie gives the chamber height as $230.09 \pm 0.15 \mathcal{P}$, which converts to $11.1617 \pm 0.0073 \mathcal{C}$.

Petrie points out that the chamber size appears to have been altered by earthquakes. We know of major quakes in 885, 1068, 1303 (which dislodged the casing stones), 1754, 1847, and 1856 CE, and there were likely many more before those. One consequence is the uneven floor, hence the varying heights.

An intended design height of 11.18 \mathcal{C} , as used by Spivey, produces interesting mathematics as discussed below, so Occam's Razor suggests that it is probably correct. It's about 1 cm more than 11.16 \mathcal{C} , or about 6 mm more than Petrie's upper bound. Petrie himself (§155) accepts that the target height was $\sqrt{125} \mathcal{C}$, which is 11.18 \mathcal{C} , albeit, according to Petrie, with a slightly different cubit value. Petrie also noticed the height being half the floor diagonal, and described it as "elegant."

The height in inches is curiously close to the pyramid side length in metres: 230.384 m.

However, accepting 11.18 \mathcal{C} raises some issues. Neither 11.16 nor 11.18 works in accepted "digits." For example, 0.18 \mathcal{C} is fractionally over 5 digits or a hand, which is 0.17857 \mathcal{C} . In this respect, it reminds me of the coffer dimensions [1], where neither the width at 1.87 \mathcal{C} , nor the length at 4.347 \mathcal{C} , are digit or palm lengths.

Indeed, it implies that the builders used a cubit divided into 100 and 1000 parts, like a modern metre stick, rather than into 28 digits as per extant cubit rods. Petrie (§139) mentions seeing evidence of the use of a decimal cubit, even if we have not yet found any examples.

Fig. 5 shows how part of such a cubit rod might look, compared to a metric ruler. For some reason, it shrinks from true size when printed.

Figure 4: The probable intended coffer with lid dimensions

Figure 5: Centimetres and millimetres compared to decimal centicubit and millicubit divisions.

Converting 11.18 G to metres gives 5.853848 m, which looks innocuous, but is actually $\varphi^2\sqrt{5}$.

$$\varphi^2\sqrt{5} = 2.618 \times 2.236 = 5.853848$$

Indeed, φ^2 , 5, and $\sqrt{5}$ are recurrent themes in the dimensions. Consider these cubit values:

The diagonal of the floor or ceiling, is

$$\text{Diagonal} = \sqrt{20^2 + 10^2} = \sqrt{500} = 22.36 = 10\sqrt{5}$$

The visible area of the long walls is

$$\text{Area} = 20 \times 11.18 = 223.6 = 100\sqrt{5}$$

The visible area of short walls is half that of the long walls, i.e..

$$\text{Area} = 10 \times 11.18 = 111.8 = 50\sqrt{5}$$

The volume of the chamber is

$$\text{Volume} = 20 \times 10 \times 11.18 = 2236 = 1000\sqrt{5}$$

A cube with the same volume would have side $\sqrt[3]{2236} = 13.07647235$ G.

This is close to $5\varphi^2$. The actual value is 4.9948382829 φ^2 .

$5 \times \varphi^2 = 13.09$ (rounded).

The 20×10 G “double square” floor design gives us φ by default (Fig. 6):

$$(\text{diagonal} + \text{short side}) \div \text{long side} = (10\sqrt{5} + 10) \div 20 = \varphi$$

There is another double square, based vertically on the floor diagonal (Fig. 7):

$$(\text{chamber diagonal} + \text{height}) \div \text{floor diagonal} = (5 \times 5 + 5\sqrt{5}) \div 10\sqrt{5} = \varphi$$

There is a further relationship to φ , in “heaven over earth” style. A line drawn up the corner, across the ceiling and down the other side, divided by the length (Fig. 8):

Figure 6: Double square leading to $\sqrt{5}$ and φ

Figure 7: Vertical double square leading to φ

Figure 8: Another φ

$$(\text{height} + \text{width} + \text{height}) \div \text{length} = (11.18 + 10 + 11.18) \div 20 = \varphi$$

A similar approach gives us φ^2 , using the diagonals on the short wall. (Fig. 9):

$$(\text{height} + \text{diagonal} + \text{diagonal} + \text{height}) \div \text{length} = (11.18 + 15 + 15 + 11.18) \div 20 = \varphi^2$$

It is clear that the architects revered $\sqrt{5}$ and its offspring, the golden ratio. They also used a $1000\sqrt{5}$ G double square for the site plan [8] (Fig. 2).

6 Pi π

The walls famously extend down below the floor, and are detached from the floor (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Smyth's diagram of the bottom of the walls [10].

Petrie (§155) gives the average distance from floor to base of wall as $5.11 \pm 0.12 \dot{P}$. Adding this to the chamber height of 230.09 gives us, including the uncertainty, a height of 234.93 to 235.49 \dot{P} , which converts to 11.3965 to 11.423 \dot{G} . Given my understanding of how the designers thought, I would posit that the intended target was 11.416 or 11.42. 11.416 is doable with a decimal cubit. From the mason's point of view, there is no difference in working to 11.420 or 11.416... you measure, mark, and remove the excess. Exactly how that is done is left as a thought exercise for the reader.

Petrie (§52) gives the average of the first four courses as $47.045 \pm 0.051 \dot{P}$, and the top course as $47.040 \pm 0.013 \dot{P}$. I propose the lower four courses were 2.284 \dot{G} , and the top course 2.280 \dot{G} . Then $(4 \times 2.284) + 2.280 = 11.416$. Checking against Petrie, 2.284 \dot{G} is 47.0828 \dot{P} , and 2.280 \dot{G} is 47.0004 \dot{P} . To get greater equivalence, you could reduce two of the lower courses by 0.001 \dot{G} , and increase the top course by 0.002 \dot{G} . That would give $2.284 + 2.283 + 2.284 + 2.283$, average 2.2835 which is 47.0725 \dot{P} , and 2.282 \dot{G} which is 47.0416 \dot{P} .

It may be misguided to assume that the courses are uniform... the figures that Smyth quotes from Aiton & Ingles [10], for example, have the top row varying from 45.5 to 48 \dot{P} , a difference of 6.35 cm. Their figures do imply an alternating pattern in course height.

Petrie then confirms a theory current at his time, that the "circuit" (perimeter) of the long wall, divided by the length, gives π .

$$\text{Perimeter} \div \text{Length} = (20 + 11.416 + 20 + 11.416) \div 20 = 62.832 \div 20 = 3.1416$$

A simpler approach is to note that $(\text{length} + \text{height}) = 20 + 11.416 = 31.416 = 10\pi$.

The perimeter of the chamber is

$$\text{Perimeter} = 20 + 10 + 20 + 10 = 60 \dot{G} = 31.416 \text{ m} = 10\pi \text{ m}$$

The diagonal of the long wall (chamber height, not wall height) is

$$\text{Diagonal} = \sqrt{20^2 + 11.18^2} = 22.91271263 \dot{G}$$

The perimeter divided by φ^2 is

$$60 \div 2.618 = 22.91825821 \dot{G}$$

The difference is 0.005545583 \dot{G} , or 2.9 mm on a length of 11.997 metres.

This suggests that the diagonal is intended to relate to the perimeter via φ^2 .

If we work in metres, and take the diagonal as 12 metres, then we have

$$12\varphi^2 = 10\pi, \text{ or } 6\varphi^2 = 5\pi, \text{ or } \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \frac{\pi}{6}$$

Which brings us back to the classic relationships between the irrationals as lengths in metres, and the cubit, correct to four decimals:

$$\pi - \varphi^2 = \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\varphi^2 + \pi}{5 + 6} = \frac{2\pi - \varphi^2}{7} = \frac{5\varphi e}{6 \cdot 7} = \frac{7\varphi\pi}{5^2 e} = \left(\frac{\varphi + 1}{e - 1} - 1 \right) = \left(\frac{\pi + 1}{e} - 1 \right) = \mathfrak{C}$$

7 Conclusion

These observations reinforce evidence seen in my other papers about the walls [3] and floor [4], or the Giza site in general [8], that the builders were familiar with square roots, the golden ratio, and pi. The known mathematical papyruses do not use any of those, so it is likely that the 4th dynasty was not familiar with them, yet π , φ , and square roots are used all over Giza. Thus the 4th dynasty as we know them could not have created Giza.

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